

Experiment on elicitation of context-aware features

May 2021

Have you ever heard of
“context-aware features”?

- Context-aware functionalities are functionalities that consider context to produce a certain system behavior, typically an adaptation or recommendation.

Example 1: YouTube (adaptation)

Example 2: Gmail (recommendation)

Early RE: context modeling

DORFFUNK

VIDEO

Today's experiment

To participate in this restricted survey, you need a valid token.

If you have been issued a token, please enter it in the box below and click continue.

* Token:

Continue

C5.2 - Experiment with practitioners

Welcome to the activity on elicitation of context-aware features. This is a controlled experiment and the participation is anonymous.

Confidentiality: To help protect your confidentiality, this instrument does not contain any information that could personally identify you. All data will be stored in a password-protected location. Your responses will be kept confidential. The anonymized data will be available to all researchers involved in this project. The raw data collected will not be shared with third parties at any time. Any insights gained will be used in the context of doctoral research. This may also include publication of the results (including aggregation of responses) in scientific publications. The raw data will be deleted as soon as it is no longer needed for the stated purposes, but no later than at the end of the doctoral research.

I consent to participate.

Next

Download here the artifact (PDF)

After the download, please open the file in a new window.

Then, click on NEXT in this page.

 If you have problems downloading and/or opening this PDF file, please contact the moderator.

Next

Write down a requirement that adds context-aware functionality to the user task [REDACTED]

🔍 List of contextual elements that are available for you to use:

Entity	Contextual element	Description	Values
User	<u>User</u>	The user who is using the app.	-

***Is there still time?**

! Choose one of the following answers

YES!

No, time is over.

Next

Write down another requirement that adds context-aware functionality to the user task

🔗 List of contextual elements that are available for you to use:

Entity	Contextual element	Description	Values
User	<u>User</u>	The user who is using the app.	-

***Is there still time?**

📌 Choose one of the following answers

YES!

No, time is over.

Next

1. There is NO right or wrong in this activity; just do it as good as you can.
2. There is NO minimum number of requirements that you have to create.
3. Once you finish a requirement, move to the next.

30 minutes

And the user task to be improved via context awareness is...

CREATE A COMMENT

Mike takes his phone and launches DorfFunk to check out what is new in his community

He sees the post of Lena in the feed. She is asking for information about bakeries in the town. Mike clicks on it

Mike reads all comments and an idea for Lena comes to his mind

He starts to write a comment

Mike also wants to add some pictures of the bread that he did by himself last weekend

He selects the pictures from the gallery

He checks the pictures

**Mike finishes
writing his
comment and sends
it**

How to improve this user task with context awareness?

- Remember of the task in focus: CREATE A COMMENT
- Remember to use only the contextual elements that are available
 - For example: “location“ is NOT available for you to use!

Write requirements as specific as possible

- Depending on the network connection of the user, the system shall adapt the video quality automatically. (bad example)
- When the network connection of the user has LOW BANDWIDTH, set the video quality to LOW automatically (good example)

Here you go